

Appendix to Modal and Symbolic Trace Logic

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This appendix provides additional material for the paper “Modal and Symbolic Trace Logic”,
20 submitted to the *Journal of Logic and Algebraic Methods*. Numbered (sub-)sections correspond to those of the paper.

3. Modal Trace Logic

Remark 1 (Syntax of the Trace Modality). The trace modality does not look like a classic “modality”. This is a syntactic difference only. Instead of $[C_{impl} \Vdash_{\alpha} C_{spec}]$, we could write $[C_{impl}]_{\alpha} C_{spec}$. We decided against this to clearly scope the specification, and to emphasize that abstraction is applied to the left *and* the right-hand side. \diamond

Remark 2 (Trace Modality Semantics in Original Paper). The advantage of the semantics in [1] is that the *approximating* nature of the trace modality is made more explicit by the use of set inclusion: the traces of the specification are a superset of, i.e., approximate, the traces of the implementation. Our new semantics, in turn, is a uniform extension of the semantics of the box modality of Propositional Dynamic Logic (PDL) [2] to the trace semantics setting (augmented by the use of abstraction and initial states). In PDL, the semantics of a box modality formula is the set of *states* satisfying the property that *if* they are initial states of a terminating transition of the program in the box, *then* the final states are elements of the semantics of the postcondition. The semantics of a PDL program are the pairs of initial and final states. In our framework, *all* Trace Description Language (TDL) constructs are semantically represented by *trace sets*. \diamond

Remark 3 (Semantics of Postconditions). We defined the semantics of first-order postconditions and LTL formulas as sets of traces starting in state σ . This implies that such a formula *never can be universally valid* in Modal Trace Logic (MTL): since $tval(K, \sigma | \varphi)$ has to cover the whole universe $Traces$ of traces, but only produces traces starting in σ , not even " \models true" holds. We briefly discuss motivation, alternatives and remedies:

- Expressions such as $[\varphi \Vdash_{\alpha} p]$ can only be valid if valuations of φ do not start in different states than p . We intended to enable such applications of the trace modality; for instance, to describe that φ is a precise summary of p .
- For reasoning about validity of φ in MTL, one can use “true $\subset \varphi$ ” instead. Its semantics is $tval(K, \sigma | \text{true}) \cup tval(K, \sigma | \varphi)$; traces not starting in σ are in $tval(K, \sigma | \text{true})$. The MTL formula is valid iff φ is universally valid in the classical sense.
- Alternatively defining $K, \sigma, \beta \models \mathcal{C}$ to hold iff $tval(K, \sigma, \beta | \mathcal{C}) = Traces_{\sigma}$ (traces starting in σ) would yield a weaker notion of validity for the trace modality as the one in [1] though, since traces added by α not starting in σ (which may exist) would not have to be considered.
- We could have defined validity *directly* as in [1] without the detour via the general framework of MTL. Then, we would lose the uniformity of MTL; also, the meaning of expressions such as $[\mathcal{C}_1 \Vdash_{\alpha} [\mathcal{C}_2 \Vdash_{\alpha'} \mathcal{C}_3]]$ is not clear if the trace modality has no trace semantics. \diamond

Below, we prove the result for axiom **K** of modal logic: it does not hold in general for MTL, but for the identity abstraction, and for big-step abstraction with first-order postconditions.

PROOF (AXIOM K). The scheme of axiom **K** is in our framework, due to the definition of $tval(K, \sigma | \varphi \subset \psi)$ as $tval(K, \sigma | \varphi) \cup tval(K, \sigma | \psi)$, equivalent to the following equation, for any K, σ :

$$Traces = \left(\overline{tval(K, \sigma | [\mathcal{C}_1 \Vdash_{\alpha} tval(K, \sigma | \mathcal{C}_2) \cup tval(K, \sigma | \mathcal{C}_3])]} \cup \left(\overline{tval(K, \sigma | [\mathcal{C}_1 \Vdash_{\alpha} \mathcal{C}_2])} \cup tval(K, \sigma | [\mathcal{C}_1 \Vdash_{\alpha} \mathcal{C}_3]) \right) \right)$$

Based on the semantics of the trace modality and laws of set theory, this is equivalent to

$$Traces = \alpha \left(\overline{tval(K, \sigma | \mathcal{C}_2)} \right) \cap \alpha (tval(K, \sigma | \mathcal{C}_2)) \cup \alpha (tval(K, \sigma | \mathcal{C}_1)) \cup \alpha (tval(K, \sigma | \mathcal{C}_3))$$

Axiom **K** holds iff any trace τ is in the right set. If τ is *no* trace of the abstracted implementation \mathcal{C}_1 or *is* a trace of the abstracted postcondition \mathcal{C}_3 , this is the case. Conversely, let $\tau \in \alpha (tval(K, \sigma | \mathcal{C}_1))$, but $\tau \notin \alpha (tval(K, \sigma | \mathcal{C}_3))$. Such a trace generally exists for postconditions which are no theorems, and abstractions that are not too coarse. Then, axiom **K** holds iff

$$\tau \notin \alpha \left(\overline{tval(K, \sigma | \mathcal{C}_2)} \right) \cap \alpha (tval(K, \sigma | \mathcal{C}_2)). \quad (1)$$

40 A sufficient condition for this to hold is that α is also homomorphic on intersections, i.e., $\alpha(A) \cap \alpha(B) = \alpha(A \cap B)$ (since also $\alpha(\emptyset) = \emptyset$). This is not generally necessary and does not hold for many sensible abstractions. For example, if p and q are *different* programs with *the same final states*, we have

$$\alpha_{big}(tval(K, \sigma|p)) \cap \alpha_{big}(tval(K, \sigma|q)) = \alpha_{big}(tval(K, \sigma|p)) = \alpha_{big}(tval(K, \sigma|q)),$$

while $\alpha_{big}(tval(K, \sigma|p) \cap tval(K, \sigma|q)) = \alpha_{big}(\emptyset) = \emptyset$.

45 Nonetheless, for many combinations of abstractions and TDLs, axiom **K** *does* hold. In particular, Eq. (1) is always true for $\alpha = \alpha_{id}$. Also, the combination of big-step abstraction α_{big} and first-order postconditions for \mathcal{C}_2 and \mathcal{C}_3 behaves well, in both variants α_{big}^- and α_{big}^+ . In the latter case, the abstraction does not add traces to the semantics of first-order formulas \mathcal{C}_2 (thus, Eq. (1) holds). In the former case, it adds infinite traces, but those will then also be in $\alpha_{big}(tval(K, \sigma|\mathcal{C}_3))$. \square

50 *Relation to Dynamic Logic.* To examine the properties of (propositional) Dynamic Logic (DL) w.r.t. the trace modality, we embed the language of regular abstract DL programs [2]. A DL program consists of *atomic* programs a, b, c, \dots and the following program operators, where β, γ are programs:

Name	Example	Intuition
; composition	$\beta; \gamma$	“Execute β , then execute γ .”
\cup choice	$\beta \cup \gamma$	“Choose β or γ nondeterministically and execute it.”
* iteration	β^*	“Execute β a nondeterministically chosen finite number of times (zero or more).”
? test	$\varphi?$	“Test φ ; proceed if true, fail if false.”

Following [2], we define the semantics of compound PDL programs as:

$$\begin{aligned} tval(K, \sigma|\beta; \gamma) &:= \{\sigma_1 \cdots \sigma_i \cdots \sigma_n \mid \sigma_1 \cdots \sigma_i \in tval(K, \sigma|\beta) \text{ and} \\ &\quad \sigma_i \cdots \sigma_n \in tval(K, \sigma|\gamma)\} \\ tval(K, \sigma|\beta \cup \gamma) &:= tval(K, \sigma|\beta) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\gamma) \\ tval(K, \sigma|\beta^*) &:= \{\sigma\sigma \mid \sigma \in \mathcal{S}\} \cup tval(K, \sigma|\beta) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\beta; \beta) \cup \dots \\ tval(K, \sigma|\varphi?) &:= \{\sigma\sigma \mid K, \sigma \models \varphi\} \end{aligned}$$

55 The subsequent Lem. 1 establishes that only one axiom of the axiomatic system of PDL [2, Sect. 5.5] generally holds for the trace modality (the axiom (iv) for choice); the axiom for a conjunctive postcondition, axiom (iii), holds without abstraction. Axiom (ii) of the system of is axiom **K**, item (i) are the standard axioms of propositional logic. All other axioms do not hold in MTL. For instance, the linearization axiom $[\beta; \gamma \Vdash_\alpha \varphi] \leftrightarrow [\beta \Vdash_\alpha [\gamma \Vdash_\alpha \varphi]]$ cannot be shown, since the trace modality evaluates as well the implementation as the specification starting in the same state, whereas in $\beta; \gamma$, program γ is started in the final state of β . That these axioms do not characterize MTL is not surprising: PDL is a system for postcondition reasoning, while MTL is a more flexible framework for trace inclusion. Expressing relational properties in a dynamic logic requires relatively sophisticated formalizations. Moreover, in a big-step system like PDL, finer

granularities are impossible to convey. Instead of using techniques like linearization, we perform
 65 *symbolic evaluation* of the implementation and specification; the resulting *symbolic* traces then can
 be checked inclusion (see section on STL).

Lemma 1 (Axioms of PDL). *Axiom (iii) of PDL holds for the trace modality with identity abstraction. Axiom (iv) is generally true; axioms (v) to (viii) do not hold.*

PROOF (AXIOMS OF PDL). Let β, γ, φ and ψ have a trace semantics, and α be a trace abstraction.

Axiom (iii): $[\beta \Vdash_\alpha \varphi \odot \psi] \equiv [\beta \Vdash_\alpha \varphi] \odot [\beta \Vdash_\alpha \psi]$. ✓/✗

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{tval}(K, \sigma | [\beta \Vdash_\alpha \varphi \odot \psi]) \\
 &= \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi \odot \psi)) \\
 &= \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cup (\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi) \cap \text{tval}(K, \sigma | \psi))) \\
 &\neq \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cup (\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi)) \cap \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \psi))) \\
 &= \left(\overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi)) \right) \cap \left(\overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \psi)) \right) \\
 &= [\beta \Vdash_\alpha \varphi] \odot [\beta \Vdash_\alpha \psi]
 \end{aligned}$$

70 This axiom only holds for abstractions which are homomorphic for intersections, e.g., the identity
 abstraction.

Axiom (iv): $[\beta \cup \gamma \Vdash_\alpha \varphi] \equiv [\beta \Vdash_\alpha \varphi] \odot [\gamma \Vdash_\alpha \varphi]$. ✓

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{tval}(K, \sigma | [\beta \cup \gamma \Vdash_\alpha \varphi]) \\
 &= \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta \cup \gamma))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi)) \\
 &= \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta) \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \gamma)))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi)) \\
 &= \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cup \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \gamma))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi)) \\
 &= \left(\overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cap \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \gamma))} \right) \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi)) \\
 &= \left(\overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi)) \right) \cap \left(\overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \gamma))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi)) \right) \\
 &= \text{tval}(K, \sigma | [\beta \Vdash_\alpha \varphi]) \odot \text{tval}(K, \sigma | [\gamma \Vdash_\alpha \varphi])
 \end{aligned}$$

Axiom (v): $[\beta; \gamma \Vdash_\alpha \varphi] \equiv [\beta \Vdash_\alpha [\gamma \Vdash_\alpha \varphi]]$. ✗

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{tval}(K, \sigma | [\beta; \gamma \Vdash_\alpha \varphi]) \\
 &= \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta; \gamma))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi)) \\
 &\neq \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cap \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \gamma))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi)) \\
 &= \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cup \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \gamma))} \cup \alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \varphi))
 \end{aligned}$$

The equality $\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta; \gamma)) = \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \beta))} \cap \overline{\alpha(\text{tval}(K, \sigma | \gamma))}$ only holds for special cases, e.g., big-step abstraction and constructs β, γ which do not perform conflicting changes on the state. Thus, the linearization axiom (v) does generally not hold.

Axiom (vi): $[\psi? \Vdash_{\alpha} \varphi] \equiv (\psi \subset \varphi)$. **X**

$$\begin{aligned} & [\psi? \Vdash_{\alpha} \varphi] \\ &= \overline{\alpha (tval(K, \sigma|\psi?))} \cup \alpha (tval(K, \sigma|\varphi)) \\ &\neq \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\psi)} \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varphi) \\ &= \psi \subset \varphi \end{aligned}$$

⁷⁵ This axiom only holds if ψ is *unsatisfiable*. Otherwise, the set $tval(K, \sigma|\psi)$ will almost always be different than the (usually much smaller) $\alpha (tval(K, \sigma|\psi?))$, and the traces of φ are abstracted in the left- but not the right-hand side.

Axioms (vii) and (viii): unwinding with linearization and induction axiom. **X**

⁸⁰ These axioms do also not hold since they rely on linearization, which does not work for the trace modality (see axiom (v)).

4. Formalization of Verification Tasks

Table 1 shows a concise summary of our formalizations of different program verification tasks in MTL.

Table 1: Representations of Different Verification Tasks in MTL

Task	Problem	Solution Techniques (excerpt)
Partial Correctness	$\models [p \Vdash_{\alpha_{big}^-} Post]$	Symbolic execution, weakest precondition reasoning, Hoare calculus
Total Correctness	$\models \langle p \Vdash_{\alpha_{big}^+} Post \rangle$	ditto; plus reasoning about variant / ranking function
Information Flow	$\models [p(\mathbf{l}, \mathbf{h}) \Vdash_{\alpha_{\{1\}} \circ \alpha_{big}^+} p(\mathbf{l}, \mathbf{h}')]]$	Security type systems, Hoare calculus, symbolic execution
Information Flow with Declassification	$\models \bigwedge_{i=1}^n (e_i(\mathbf{l}, \mathbf{h}) \doteq e_i(\mathbf{l}, \mathbf{h}')) \subset [p(\mathbf{l}, \mathbf{h}) \Vdash_{\alpha_{\{1\}} \circ \alpha_{big}^+} p(\mathbf{l}, \mathbf{h}')]]$	ditto
Finite Space MC	$\sigma \models [p \Vdash \xi]$	Automata constructions
Bounded MC	$\models [p \Vdash_{\alpha_p^k} \xi]$	SMT solvers for checking encoded program paths
Abstraction-Based MC	$\models [p \Vdash_{\alpha_d} \xi]$	Overapproximation techniques, CEGAR loops
Symbolic Execution-Based MC	$\models [p \Vdash \xi]$	Invariant generation, k -induction
Bug Finding	$\models \langle p \Vdash \neg \xi \rangle$	All MC techniques; can be integrated with all abstractions
Program Synthesis	$\models [p' \Vdash_{\alpha_{big}^+} p]$	Proof-theoretic synthesis, proof mining
Correct compilation	$\models [c \Vdash_{\alpha_{obs} \circ \alpha_{big}^+} p]$	Simultaneous symbolic execution, compiler extraction from executable HOL specifications
Program evolution / Bug fixing	$\models [p_{fixed} \Vdash_{\alpha_{patch} \circ \alpha_{big}^+} p_{buggy}]$ $\models [p_{buggy} \Vdash_{\alpha_{bug} \circ \alpha_{big}^+} p_{fixed}]$	Manual program refinement, automatic software repair

4.1. Functional Verification

Remark 4 (Proving Termination). Normal completion (including termination) only is, for *deterministic* programs, expressed as $\langle p \Vdash_{\alpha_{big}^+} \text{true} \rangle$: Since $\alpha_{big}^+(tval(K, \sigma | \text{true}))$ contains all *finite* traces, traces of p have to be finite. For nondeterministic programs, we can reason about *termination* using $[p \Vdash_{\alpha_{big}^+} \text{true}]$; this, however, allows p to complete abruptly, i.e., to evaluate to the empty trace set. The diamond modality is not useful for nondeterministic programs since only *one* trace starting in σ has to be finite. \diamond

85 4.3. Software Model Checking

In the following, we formalize four popular Software Model Checking (SMC) approaches in MTL. Formulas ξ are Temporal Logic (TL) formulas.

Finite Space MC Finite space model checkers exhaustively explore the state space of an abstract program model. This implies that the analysis starts from *a concrete input state* σ and that
90 no unbounded data structures are involved. We formalize this problem as $\sigma \models [p \Vdash \xi]$.

Bounded MC (BMC) Bounded Model Checking (BMC) [3,4] handles unbounded data structures, but restricts the search space according to a predefined upper bound on the number of loop executions. This problem can be expressed as $\models [p \Vdash_{\alpha_p^k} \xi]$, where α_p^k adds all traces of p with more than k loop executions (and recursive method calls).

95 **Abstraction-Based MC** uses data abstraction to limit the search space. We express it as $\models [p \Vdash_{\alpha_d} \xi]$, where α_d is an abstract interpretation of the data types of p .

Symbolic Execution-Based MC is similar to functional verification. They differ in the abstraction (identity vs. big-step) and that in MC, less complex properties are proven: $\models [p \Vdash \xi]$.

5. Symbolic Trace Logic

100 5.1. Symbolic Traces and Translations

Remark 5 (Empty Traces vs. Empty Trace Sets). The semantics of the empty symbolic trace \perp (the empty trace ε), is different from the *empty trace set* to which a Symbolic Execution State (SES) with unsatisfiable path condition evaluates: $tval(K, \sigma | (\text{false}, \mathcal{U})) = \emptyset$. The empty trace is the neutral element of concatenation ($\varepsilon\tau = \tau$). However, concatenations where one part evaluates to the empty set evaluate to the empty trace set, too. This is used for the choice operator: if path conditions are mutually exclusive, exactly one of $tval(K, \sigma | \varpi)$ and $tval(K, \sigma | \varpi')$ is non-empty. A PDL test φ can be realized by adding φ to the path condition of the next SES. \diamond

The following concrete example shows how to translate a simple loop-free program to a symbolic trace. It also exemplifies the application of symbolic trace abstraction.

Example 1 (Symbolic Trace Translation and Abstraction for Programs). Consider the following program p (in Java syntax) computing the difference of two integers **a** and **b**:

```
res=0; if (b < a) { tmp=a; a=b; b=tmp; } res=b-a;
```

The symbolic trace translation p^s has the shape

$$\begin{aligned} &(\text{true}) \diamond (\text{res} := 0) \diamond (((b < a) \diamond ((\text{tmp} := a) \diamond (a := b) \diamond (b := \text{tmp}))) + \\ &((b \geq a) \diamond \perp)) \diamond (\text{res} := b - a) \end{aligned}$$

By evaluating the composition operator \diamond and finally rewriting sequential updates to parallel ones, we simplify this symbolic trace to

$$\begin{aligned} &(\text{true}); (\text{res} := 0); ((b < a, \text{res} := 0 \parallel \text{tmp} := a); (b < a, \text{res} := 0 \parallel \text{tmp} := a \parallel a := b); \\ & (b < a, \text{res} := 0 \parallel \text{tmp} := a \parallel a := b \parallel b := a); \\ & (b < a, \text{tmp} := a \parallel a := b \parallel b := a \parallel \text{res} := a - b)) + \\ & ((b \geq a, \text{res} := 0); (b \geq a, \text{res} := b - a)) \end{aligned}$$

Applying the symbolic equivalent of big-step abstraction α_{big}^- to the resulting trace leads to

$$(\text{true}); \top^\infty; ((b < a, \text{tmp} := a \parallel a := b \parallel b := a \parallel \text{res} := a - b) + (b \geq a, \text{res} := b - a))$$

This trace represents all finite traces of at least two states, where the last one is represented by the SESs in the choice expression. All of these satisfy the postcondition $\text{res} \geq 0$. The symbolic equivalent of α_{big}^+ would insert \top instead of \top^∞ , if there are no \top^∞ or \circ^ω elements in the abstracted trace. We can also symbolically represent, for example, the combined abstraction $\alpha_{big}^- \circ \alpha_{\{\text{res}\}}$, which produces the trace $(\text{true}); \top^\infty; ((b < a, \text{res} := a - b) + (b \geq a, \text{res} := b - a))$. \diamond

5.2. Symbolic Translation of Loops

The following example demonstrates a use case for *underapproximating* loop invariants for the specification part of the trace modality in a relational verification scenario.

Example 2 (Underapproximating Loop Invariants). To motivate the use of actually underapproximating loop invariants, i.e., loop descriptions of a *strict subset* of possible behavior, assume a WHILE language with a choice statement “ p_1 **or** p_2 ”, which nondeterministically chooses either p_1 or p_2 and then executes it. Let

```
 $p_{impl} := \text{while } (i > 0) \text{ } i--;$      $p_{spec} := \text{while } (i > 0) \{ i--; \text{or } \{i--; i--\}; \}$ 
```

The traces for p_{impl} are

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcup_{K, \sigma} (tval(K, \sigma | p_{impl})) = & \{ \sigma \sigma \mid \sigma(i) \leq 0 \} \cup \\ & \{ \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \cdots \sigma_n \mid \sigma = \sigma_1 \wedge \sigma(i) > 0 \wedge \sigma_n(i) = 0 \wedge \\ & \quad \forall 0 < k < n; \sigma_k(i) - \sigma_{k+1}(i) = 1 \}. \end{aligned}$$

They are finite; the loop is not entered because \mathbf{i} is initially zero or negative, or \mathbf{i} is decreased by 1 in every iteration, until it equals 0 and the program terminates. The traces of p_{spec} have the shape

$$\bigcup_{K, \sigma} (tval(K, \sigma | p_{spec})) = \{\sigma\sigma \mid \sigma(\mathbf{i}) \leq 0\} \cup \{\sigma_1\sigma_2 \cdots \sigma_n \mid \sigma = \sigma_1 \wedge \sigma(\mathbf{i}) > 0 \wedge (\sigma_n(\mathbf{i}) = 0 \vee \sigma_n(\mathbf{i}) = -1) \wedge \forall 0 < k < n; 1 \leq \sigma_k(\mathbf{i}) - \sigma_{k+1}(\mathbf{i}) \leq 2\}.$$

110 This is a superset of the traces of p_{impl} : if in every iteration of p_{spec} the left branch of the **or** is chosen, we obtain a trace of p_{impl} for every initial state σ_0 . It is a *strict* superset since it also contains traces terminating quicker or have final states where \mathbf{x} attains the value -1 instead of 0.

A *precise* loop invariant for p_{impl} is $\mathbf{i} \geq 0$; together with the negated guard, $\mathbf{i} \leq 0$, this allows to deduce the *exact* final value of \mathbf{i} , 0. The simplest overapproximating (i.e., imprecise) loop invariant is “true”; another, more precise one is $\mathbf{i} \geq -1$. The latter is in fact a precise invariant for p_{spec} , which we can use to abstract the loop if we also use big-step abstraction. However, in a proof of $[p_{impl} \Vdash_{\alpha_{big}^+} p_{spec}]$, we might also use $\mathbf{i} \geq 0$ as invariant for p_{spec} . This invariant describes *some* of the traces of p_{spec} , but not all—it is an *underapproximating* loop invariant, which is, however, “abstract enough”, since it describes all traces of p_{impl} . It would be unsound to use it in a proof of the converse $[p_{spec} \Vdash_{\alpha_{big}^+} p_{impl}]$, which we then could prove *although it is invalid*. \diamond

5.5. Soundness, (In)completeness, and Example

The sequent calculus for Symbolic Trace Logic (STL) is sound, but incomplete. Subsequently, 115 we prove soundness of all rules of STL, from which the soundness of the calculus follows. Also, we prove completeness for the rules which are complete. We begin with introducing a *sufficient* condition for proving soundness and completeness of STL rules at once. After the proofs, we provide material related to applications of the STL calculus mentioned in the main paper.

Lemma 2. *Let $\Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1, \dots, \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n$ be the premises and $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ be the conclusion of an STL calculus rule. The rule is sound and complete if for all K, σ it holds that $tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1) \cap \dots \cap tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n) = tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma \vdash \Delta)$.*

PROOF. We may assume

$$tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1) \cap \dots \cap tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n) = tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma \vdash \Delta). \quad (2)$$

Soundness: Assume that $\Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1, \dots, \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n$ are universally valid. Then, for each $i = 1, \dots, n$, it holds for all K, σ that $tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma_i \vdash \Delta_i) = Traces$. Then, however, also the for the intersection 125 we have $tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1) \cap \dots \cap tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n) = Traces$. Due to Eq. (2), this equals $tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma \vdash \Delta)$; it follows that $K, \sigma \Vdash \Gamma \vdash \Delta$, and thus $\Vdash \Gamma \vdash \Delta$.

Completeness: Assume that $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ is universally valid; therefore, for all K, σ , it holds that $tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma \vdash \Delta) = Traces$. Due to Eq. (2), we have

$$tval(K, \sigma | tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1) \cap \dots \cap tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n)) = Traces,$$

which implies, for each $i = 1, \dots, n$, $tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n) = Traces$, and thus $\Vdash \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n$. \square

130 The condition of Lem. 2 is not *necessary* since it requires that the *same* structure and state satisfy all premises and the conclusion of a rule, which is too strict. It is, however, useful since it allows to reduce soundness *and* completeness of a rule to a single equation. Furthermore, the condition is even necessary for (sound and complete) rules which do not introduce new program variables and rigid symbols, which applies to all our rules.

135 We now show the proof for the STL calculus rules.

PROOF (SOUNDNESS AND (IN-)COMPLETENESS OF STL CALCULUS RULES). +left:

$$\bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi + \varpi') \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)}.$$

+right:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \cap \bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \right) \cap \\ & \quad \left(\bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \cap \bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \right) \\ \text{de Morgan} \stackrel{=}{=} & \left(\bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)} \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \right) \cap \\ & \quad \left(\bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi')} \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \right) \\ \text{dist.} \stackrel{=}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{\left(tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \cap tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \right) \cup \bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \text{invol.} \stackrel{=}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{\overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \cap tval(K, \sigma|\varpi')} \cup \bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \text{de Morgan} \stackrel{=}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi')} \cap \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \text{def.} \stackrel{=}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi + \varpi')} \cap \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \end{aligned}$$

-left:

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \cap \bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \text{de Morgan} \stackrel{=}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)} \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \text{def.} \stackrel{=}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\neg\varpi)} \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \end{aligned}$$

-right:

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \cup \bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \text{de Morgan} \stackrel{=}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{\overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)} \cap \bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\neg\varpi) \cap \bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)}$$

elim \top^∞ :

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\top^\infty; \varpi) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'; \varpi) \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \{\tau \in \text{Traces} \mid \neg \text{finite}(\tau)\} \cup \{\tau\tau' \mid \text{finite}(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)\} \cup \\ & \{\tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \mid \neg \text{finite}(\tau)\} \cup \\ & \{\tau\tau' \mid \tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \wedge \text{finite}(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)\} \cup \\ & \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{(\star)}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \{\tau \in \text{Traces} \mid \neg \text{finite}(\tau)\} \cup \{\tau\tau' \mid \text{finite}(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)\} \cup \\ & \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\top^\infty; \varpi) \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \end{aligned}$$

where (\star) means elimination of subsets in unions, i.e., $A \subseteq B$ iff $B \cup A = B$.

elim \top :

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\top; \varpi) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'; \varpi) \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \{\tau\tau' \mid \text{finite}(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)\} \cup \\ & \{\tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \mid \neg \text{finite}(\tau)\} \cup \\ & \{\tau\tau' \mid \tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \wedge \text{finite}(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)\} \cup \\ & \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{(\dagger)}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \{\tau\tau' \mid \text{finite}(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)\} \cup \\ & \{\tau\tau' \mid \tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \wedge \text{finite}(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)\} \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{(\star)}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \{\tau\tau' \mid \text{finite}(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)\} \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\top; \varpi) \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \end{aligned}$$

where (\dagger) means that ϖ' cannot have infinite traces, since due to the definition of the semantics of symbolic traces, only symbolic traces with occurrences of \top^∞ or $(\varpi'')^\omega$ (for any ϖ'') represent infinite traces, which is excluded; and (\star) is as for elim \top^∞ .

¹⁴⁰ elim \top : This proof does not work by Lem. 2, since the rule is *incomplete*: since we discard the context, one or both premises can be invalid, even if the conclusion *was* valid. For soundness, we have to prove that from the universal validity of the premises, the universal validity of the conclusion follows. The latter is phrased as, for any K, σ ,

$$\bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi; \varpi'') \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'; \varpi''') \cap \bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} = \text{Traces}.$$

I.e., by the semantics of symbolic traces, we have to show

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \{\tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \mid \neg finite(\tau)\} \\ & \quad \cup \{\tau\tau' \mid \tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \wedge finite(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'')\} \supseteq \\ & \quad (\{\tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \mid \neg finite(\tau)\} \\ & \quad \cup \{\tau\tau' \mid \tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \wedge finite(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi''')\}) \end{aligned}$$

where we may assume that

$$tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \supseteq tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \quad (3)$$

$$tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'') \supseteq tval(K, \sigma|\varpi''') \quad (4)$$

145 Consider a trace of Δ which is also either an infinite trace of ϖ' or a trace starting with a finite trace of ϖ' and ending with a trace of ϖ''' . In the first case, by Eq. (3) it is also an infinite trace of ϖ , so the subset relation holds. If it is a trace $\tau\tau'$, where τ is a finite trace of ϖ' and τ' a trace of ϖ''' , then by Eq. (3) it is a trace of $\varpi; \varpi'''$. Moreover, by Eq. (4), every trace of ϖ''' is also a trace of ϖ'' , therefore, $\tau\tau'$ is a trace of $\varpi; \varpi''$.

150 If the context Γ, Δ was not removed, Eqs. (3) and (4) would not be useful; each trace of, e.g., ϖ''' could then also be a trace of Γ , which would neither imply that $\tau\tau'$ is a trace of Γ nor a trace of $\varpi; \varpi''$. Therefore $\text{elim};$ had to be designed incomplete.

elim^*_1 :

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'; \varpi^*; \varpi'') \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'; \varpi'') \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \{\tau'\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n\tau'' \mid \tau_i \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \wedge \\ & \quad \tau'' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'')\} \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'; \varpi'') \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{(\star)}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup \{\tau'\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n\tau'' \mid \tau_i \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \wedge \\ & \quad \tau'' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'')\} \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi'; \varpi^*; \varpi'') \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \end{aligned}$$

pull^* :

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi^*; \varpi') \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi; \varpi^*; \varpi') \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \\ \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi^*; \varpi') \cup \{\tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \mid \neg finite(\tau)\} \cup \\ & \quad \{\tau\tau' \mid \tau \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi) \wedge finite(\tau) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma|\varpi^*; \varpi')\} \\ \stackrel{(\star)}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma|\Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma|\varpi^*; \varpi') \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma|\Delta)} \end{aligned}$$

elim^*_2 : this rule, which is similar to $\text{elim};$, is incomplete. Its soundness follows from the soundness of $\text{elim};$ together with the fact that $tval(K, \sigma|\varpi') \subseteq tval(K, \sigma|\varpi)$ implies $tval(K, \sigma|(\varpi')^*) \subseteq tval(K, \sigma|\varpi^*)$.

dupl*:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma | \varpi^*; \varpi') \cup tval(K, \sigma | \varpi^*; \varpi^*; \varpi') \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)} \\
\stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma | \varpi^*; \varpi') \cup \{\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n \mid \tau_i \in tval(K, \sigma | \varpi) \wedge \neg \text{finite}(\varpi_n)\} \cup \\
& \quad \{\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n \tau_{n+1} \cdots \tau_m \mid \tau_i \in tval(K, \sigma | \varpi) \wedge \neg \text{finite}(\varpi_m)\} \cup \\
& \quad \{\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n \tau_{n+1} \cdots \tau_m \tau' \mid \tau_i \in tval(K, \sigma | \varpi) \wedge \text{finite}(\varpi_i) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma | \varpi')\} \cup \\
& \quad \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)} \\
= & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma | \varpi^*; \varpi') \cup \{\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n \mid \tau_i \in tval(K, \sigma | \varpi) \wedge \neg \text{finite}(\varpi_n)\} \cup \\
& \quad \{\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n \tau' \mid \tau_i \in tval(K, \sigma | \varpi) \wedge \text{finite}(\varpi_i) \wedge \tau' \in tval(K, \sigma | \varpi')\} \cup \\
& \quad \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)} \\
\stackrel{(*)}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma | \varpi^*; \varpi') \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)}
\end{aligned}$$

155 Soundness and completeness for elim^{ω}_1 , pull^{ω} and dupl^{ω} follows from the proofs of elim^{*}_1 , pull^* and dupl^* , and $tval(K, \sigma | \varpi^{\omega}) \supseteq tval(K, \sigma | \varpi^*)$ (for all ϖ). For elim^{ω}_2 (incomplete), we have to consider the additional case of an infinite repetition of traces of ϖ' ; also then, since all traces of ϖ' are traces of ϖ , we can conclude soundness. The second premise is then not needed. Rule elim^{ω}_3 is similar and follows again because $tval(K, \sigma | \varpi^{\omega}) \supseteq tval(K, \sigma | \varpi^*)$.

cut:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma | \varpi) \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)} \right) \cap \\
& \quad \left(\bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma | \neg \varpi) \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)} \right) \\
\stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} & \left(\bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma | \varpi) \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)} \right) \cap \\
& \quad \left(\bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma | \varpi)} \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)} \right) \\
\stackrel{\text{dist.}}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)} \cup \left(tval(K, \sigma | \varpi) \cap \overline{tval(K, \sigma | \varpi)} \right) \\
\stackrel{\text{compl.}}{=} & \bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)}
\end{aligned}$$

160 closeSubsume: we have to prove that

$$\bigcup tval(K, \sigma | \Gamma) \cup tval(K, \sigma | (C, \mathcal{U})) \cup \overline{tval(K, \sigma | (C', \mathcal{U}'))} \cap \overline{\bigcap tval(K, \sigma | \Delta)} = \text{Traces}$$

based on the assumption that $(C, \mathcal{U}) \triangleright (C', \mathcal{U}')$. The latter is, by the definition of symbolic state subsumption, equivalent to

$$\bigcup_{\beta} \left\{ val(K, \sigma, \beta | (fpv(C) := \vec{v}) \circ U)(\sigma) \mid K, \sigma, \beta \models \bigwedge (C[\vec{v} / fpv(C)]) \right\} \supseteq \\
\bigcup_{\beta} \left\{ val(K, \sigma, \beta | (fpv(C') := \vec{v}') \circ U')(\sigma) \mid K, \sigma, \beta \models \bigwedge (C'[\vec{v}' / fpv(C')]) \right\}$$

which by the semantics of symbolic traces is the same as $tval(K, \sigma | (C, \mathcal{U})) \supseteq tval(K, \sigma | (C', \mathcal{U}'))$, or equivalently $tval(K, \sigma | (C, \mathcal{U})) \cup tval(K, \sigma | (C', \mathcal{U}')) = Traces$, thus the equation to show holds.

close and $\text{close}^{\top^\infty}$ are trivial.

closeUnsat: it suffices to show that $tval(K, \sigma | (C, \mathcal{U})) = \emptyset$, because then also

$$tval(K, \sigma | (C, \mathcal{U}); \varpi) = \emptyset$$

and the whole sequent is valid. Since for all K, σ it holds that

$$\bigcup_{\beta} \{val(K, \sigma, \beta | (fpv(\text{false}) := \vec{v}) \circ Skip)(\sigma) \mid K, \sigma, \beta \models \bigwedge (Skip[\vec{v}/fpv(\text{false})])\} \supseteq \bigcup_{\beta} \{val(K, \sigma, \beta | (fpv(C) := \vec{v}') \circ U)(\sigma) \mid K, \sigma, \beta \models \bigwedge (C[\vec{v}'/fpv(C)])\}$$

165 based on the assumption that $(\text{false}, Skip) \triangleright (C, \mathcal{U})$. This is equivalent to

$$\emptyset \supseteq \bigcup_{\beta} \{val(K, \sigma, \beta | (fpv(C) := \vec{v}') \circ U)(\sigma) \mid K, \sigma, \beta \models \bigwedge (C[\vec{v}'/fpv(C)])\}$$

and thus to $tval(K, \sigma | (C, \mathcal{U})) = \emptyset$ due to the semantics of symbolic traces.

The STL proof tree for the LTL example is shown in Fig. 1. We use centered dots “...” to abbreviate long symbolic traces; bottom-aligned dots “...” represent abbreviated premises—which anyway are removed soon by elim; and elim^*_2 applications.

170 6. Related Work

Asymmetric Product Programs. The main theorem about asymmetric products in [5] relates judgements about “refinement quadruples” $\{\varphi\} P_1 \mapsto P_2 \{\psi\}$ to left products. Informally speaking, a refinement quadruple is valid if either P_2 does not terminate, or if for each trace of P_1 , there is a corresponding trace of P_2 such that the initial states satisfy the relational precondition φ and the final states satisfy the relational postcondition ψ . This is true if there is left-product preconditioned with φ which is correct w.r.t. ψ . To state this in TDL, we introduce the *postcondition abstraction* α_ψ . Let ψ be a relational postcondition for variable-disjoint programs P_1 and P_2 . We lift ψ to a property Ψ of pairs of states. For instance, if $\psi \equiv \mathbf{x} \geq \mathbf{x}'$, Ψ contains all pairs (σ, σ') where $\sigma(\mathbf{x}) \geq \sigma'(\mathbf{x}')$. Then, $\alpha_\psi(\mathcal{T}) := \mathcal{T} \cup \{\tau' \in Traces \mid \exists \tau \in \mathcal{T}; \Psi(\text{last}(\tau), \text{last}(\tau'))\}$. We now can reduce $\models \{\varphi\} P_1 \mapsto P_2 \{\psi\}$ to $\models \varphi^{tl} \wedge \langle P_2 \Vdash \text{true} \rangle \rightarrow [P_1 \Vdash_{\alpha_\psi} P_2]$. Note that α_ψ entails big-step abstraction (of finite traces). We need the premise $\langle P_2 \Vdash \text{true} \rangle$ because the refinement quadruple is always valid whenever P_2 does not terminate. This example underlines the versatility of the trace modality and trace abstractions, and, in our opinion, makes the meaning of refinement quadruples more explicit.

185 *Tools for Unifying Verification Problems.* Some systems do not provide a common semantics for verification domains, but a framework to *implement* different analyses. They usually represent verification problems in an Intermediate Language (IL) and interface to different provers. Boogie [6] and Why3 [7] both are an IL and tool for deductive program verification. They are used as backends by verifiers for languages like C and Java. When translating MTL problems to STL, STL’s regular

190 symbolic trace language can be regarded as our “IL”. Symbolic traces are, compared to Boogie and
WhyML, less usable for direct programming, more abstract and less expressive (e.g., we cannot
directly write loops, but have to use invariants). Yet, the syntactic notion of symbolic traces is
closely related to the semantics of MTL (sets of traces), allowing *formalizing* and *proving* a problem
in a closely related framework. Moreover, MTL/STL can readily express other problems than
195 “standard” postcondition verification. The STL calculus also interfaces to different provers: which
one to use for symbolic state subsumption checking is left open.

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